

1 **Phosphatidylserine enriched molecules are actively expressed and modulated in the human embryo**
2 **during TE specification.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of a
9 group of phosphatidylserine-enriched molecules which are actively expressed and modulated in the
10 human embryo during TE specification.

11 Citations

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